

Job Stress and Employees' Adaptive Performance of the Staff of Selected Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines the effect of job stress on employees' adaptive performance of staff of selected banks in Lagos State, Nigeria. To achieve this objective, research data was collected from primary and secondary sources. A sample size of 133 respondents was chosen using Yaro Yamani method while the sample size was randomly drawn from the staff of branches of GTBank and Access Bank Plc in Lagos State. The theoretical underpinning of this study stems from the role theory and person environment fit. The data was analyzed using correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis. The result shows that the variability changes in the employees' adaptive performance could be accounted for by approximately 97% of factors related to job stress (proxied using different job stress dimensions such as job roles, physical and mental conditions of employees, and work environment). The findings also reveal that there is a significant relationship between job stress and adaptive performance of employees in banking sector in Nigeria. Giving the importance of job stress, especially in the banking sector and how to improve the adaptive performance of the employees, the study recommends that managers and supervisors should reduce all distortions of responsibilities and clarify job roles, know the kind of personality traits among the individuals in their team and improve the physical work environment to reduce pressure on employees.

Keywords: job stress, job performance and employees' adaptive performance

Background to the Study

In today's world, stress has become an integral part of human activity. It is a phenomenon that has not only psychological effects on individuals, but also has effect on individuals behaviours in the workplace and as well as their cognitive levels (Robbins, 2006). Generally, stress exists in every aspect of human dealings or life. There is almost atom of stress in every human activity or endeavor (Udu & Eke, 2018). Thus, stress has become a universal element that exists in almost all profession. It is a physiological response to both internal and external cognitive stimuli (Omeje & Agu, 2011). Stress appears, among others, unstable emotions of an individual, feeling uneasy, being alone, having trouble sleeping, smoking excessively, not being able to relax, increasing blood pressure, and experiencing digestive disorders (Iskamto et al., 2021).

According to the Iskamto et al. (2019), stress is very dangerous to the physical, emotional and mental well-being of individuals which is caused by prolonged involvement with emotionally demanding situations. The process takes place gradually, accumulatively, and over time it becomes

progressively worse. However, it is a common element in any kind of job and persons have to face it in almost every aspect of life (Daniel, 2019). Stress at work is a phenomenon that forms every aspect of work ethic and life styles. Every organization today has becoming so much complex due to the rapidly changing in business environment couple with new technological advancement and increased competition in the business world which are constantly challenging the survival of every organization (Ehsan & Ali, 2019). The desired behaviour of organizations workforce is quietly also changing due to increasing job demand which requires employees to be more flexible, positively handle change, and perform adaptively (Foss and Jensen, 2019). Job stress has significant impacts on work outcomes of every employee and considered as a major factor affecting job performance (Agolla & Ongori, 2008; Rajkumar & Swaminathan, 2013). However, the pace of change workers experience in organizations characterizes much of how workplaces operate (Bocciardi et al., 2017). Thus, employees are generally working for longer hours, as the rising levels of responsibilities require them to exert themselves even more strenuously to meet rising expectations about work performance (Daniel, 2019).

In relation to the financial sector, it is said that deposit money bank is one of the most stressful organisations. Stress occurs among the workers due to high job demand which increases risk of depressive symptoms (Theorell, Hammarström & Aronsson, 2015). Recently, the banking sector has drastically changed conventional patterns of operations due to policy changes. These changes in the fabric of work in banking sector are affecting business dynamics as new ways and methods in providing financial services keep evolving on a daily basis however, poses pressure and possibly increased risks of job stress (Ehsan & Ali, 2019).

In Nigerian banking sector, there is an increase in the number of cases of violence and stress, which result in adverse health outcomes, including depressive symptoms regarding to stress at work. Thus, the most stressful factors exist due to psychical balance of work, uncertainty at work, lack of rewards etc. The workload in this sector is very exhausting and employees also have high work demands, this is what causes employee work stress. Coupled with high turnover pressure, employees are increasingly stressed and become a workload for them to achieve their targets (Iskamto, 2021). Hence, it is believed that observable stressors within the banking environment are capable of affecting the job performance of the employees. However, the increase in difficulties at work couple with family issues of the employees may also increase their physiological vulnerability. Job stress can make a difference between the ability of families to provide material security and demands on families. Even with executives and managers, stress is an experience in the work life of every employee (Daniel, 2019).

Besides, work stress not only has impact on organisation and employee job performance but also can shape dire influence when related to health care. Therefore, the importance of work stress is emphasized nowadays by employers who seek employees with high adaptability, due to the positive outcomes that follow, such as excellent work performance, work attitude, and ability to handle stress (Daniel, 2019). Employees, who display high adaptive performance in an organization, tend to have more advantages in career opportunities unlike employees who are not adaptable to change. Those who

are unable to meet these expectations will find it very challenging to secure and maintain a job as the working environment continues to change at a rapid pace (Park & Park, 2019). An employee being able to adapt to change within an organization is more focused, and able to deal with stressful situations (Pulakos, Arad, Donovan & Plamondon, 2000). Hence, it is important for organization, especially banking industry, to understand what adaptive performance truly is and what makes an employee more adaptable than another is key knowledge that employees, and employers alike need to thrive.

Research Objectives

This study investigates the effect of job stress on employees' adaptive performance of staff of selected banks in Lagos State. Specifically, the paper seeks to analyze the stressors that mostly influence adaptive performance of employees.

Research Questions

This research aims to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the effect of job stress on employees' adaptive performance?
- 2) What are the stressors that influence adaptive performance of employees?

Conceptual Clarifications

Stress

Universally, there is no single definition of stress that has been widely accepted. Stress has been defined by various scholars, scientists and policy makers. According to Adetayo, Ajani and Olabisi (2014), the most common definitions of stress are: Stress is a stimulus (a threat) that affects the body in complex ways; in this interpretation, stress is referred to as a “stressor” that evokes complex responses of the several systems of the body; stress is a bodily responses to stressors which lead to complex reaction of body systems and cause harmful consequences to those body systems and organs to the point of an individual becoming “stressed out” and serious illness then can follow; stress is an interaction between environmental threats (stressors) and bodily reactions such that stressors affect body systems, leading to behaviour feedbacks that affect the environment, which in turn can also result to mental or physical deficits. Stress that is too heavy can threaten a person's ability to deal with the environment (Iskamto, 2021).

Stress is a general term applied to the feelings of stress in human life (Iskamto, 2021). It is any intrinsic and extrinsic stimulus that evokes around a biological response (Yaribeyg et al., (2017). In general, stress is related to both external and internal factors (Melissa, 2022). External factors include physical environment and all the situations, challenges, difficulties and expectations confronting on a daily basis. Internal factors determine the body's ability to response, and deal with, external stress-inducing factors. Internal factors, which influence the ability to handle stress, include nutritional status, overall health and fitness levels, emotional well-being, and the amount of sleep and rest (Melissa, 2022). However, an individual's reaction to stimuli or events is a very important factor in

knowing how an individual might respond and whether the stimuli will be considered stressful. Daniel (2019) highlights different types of stress;

1. **Chronic stress:** This type of stress as unrelenting demands and pressures for seemingly interminable periods of time. Chronic stress is the type that wears the individual down day after day and year after year with no visible escape. It grinds away at both emotional and health of the individual leading to breakdown and even death.
2. **Acute stress:** This type of stress is the most common and most recognizable form of stress. It is the kind of stress which the individual knows exactly why he is stressed. Acute stress usually does not caused severe or permanent damage to the body.
3. **Traumatic stress:** It is a severe stress reaction that results from a catastrophic event or intense experience such as a natural disaster, sexual assault, life-threatening accident, or participation in a combat. Here, after the initial shock and emotional fallout, many trauma victims gradually begin to recover. But for some people, the psychological and physical symptoms triggered by the trauma do not go away, the body does not return to equilibrium, and life does not return to normal. This condition is known as post trauma stress disorder. Common symptoms of this type of stress are flashbacks or nightmares about the trauma, avoidance of places and things associated with the trauma, hyper vigilance for signs of danger and irritability and tension.
4. **Episodic acute stress:** Where the individual experiencing this type of stress lives are very chaotic, out of control and they always seem to be facing multiple stressful situation. They are always in a rush, always late, always taking on too many projects, handling too many demands. Those who are prone to this type of stress include “Type A” personality types. If an individual is prone to episodic acute stress, he may not know it or admit it. He may be wedded to a life style that promotes stress. Unfortunately, people with episodic acute stress may find it so habitual that they resist changing their lifestyles until they experience severe physical symptoms.

In fact, stress is something ordinary caused by several factors, as it can occur either at home or at workplace. In organizational context, stress emanates due to pressure relating to job demands. Job stress occurs when resources are “threatened, lost, and believed to be unstable, or when individuals or groups cannot see a path to the fostering and protection of their resources through their individual or joint efforts” (Eli Alvin, 2021). According to Daniel (2019), stress is an increasing problem in organizations and often cause adverse effects on performance. Work stress experienced by employees can harm the organisation because of the imbalance between productivity and the costs incurred to pay salaries, benefits, and other facilities (Iskamto 2020; Iskamoto, Ghazali, and Aftanorhan 2019). Job stress is a phenomenon that affects employees differently, in different work contexts (Iskamto, 2021). When employees develop various stress symptoms that can interfere with their performance people who experience stress can become nervous and feel chronic worries (Iskamto, 2021).

Stress related with a job is known as occupational stress or job stress. Job stress is described as a situation where job related factors interact with the employee to change, which could disrupt or enhance his/her psychological and or physiological conditions such that the person is forced to deviate from normal functioning (Udu & Eke, 2018). Occupational stress can also be defined as the harmful

physical and emotional responses occur when the requirement of job do not match capabilities, resources or need of the worker. Occupational stress occurs when there is divergence between the demands of the workplace and an individual's ability to carry out and complete these demands. It can also be seen as the inability to cope with the pressure because of poor fit between someone's abilities and job requirements and conditions which affect an individual's productivity, effectiveness, personal health and quality of work (Udu & Eke, 2018).

Ivancevich, Konopaske and Matteson (2008) and Kreitner and Kincki (2010) presented four levels of stressors in the individual life.

- (1) Individual level which consists of role conflict, role ambiguity and role overload, boredom and routine under load jobs.
- (2) Group levels consist of lack of cohesiveness inside the same group and groups' conflict.
- (3) Organizational level consists of culture, organizational structure, technology, organizational change and the style of leadership, and
- (4) Non-work stressors consist of family, age, quality of life and economic factors.

Stress sometimes may have both positive and negative impact on organization but the negative side outpaced the positive side. On the positive side, stress can spur workers to go the extra mile and maximize capabilities and potentials; it can help them to work more productively while it is capable of affecting their productivity negatively (Akinleye & Hassan, 2014). Thus, stress can eventually affect both physical and emotional wellbeing of employees. It is recognized globally as a major challenge to mental and physical health of employees which in turn affect organizational performance (Akinleye & Hassan, 2014; Ejiogu, 2006). However, stressed workers are more likely to be unhealthy, poorly motivated, less productive and less safe at work. And their organizations are likely to be affected negatively and less to succeed in a competitive business environment.

Adaptive Performance

Adaptability can be regarded as the outcome of self-regulation *parsi*, it is a less proactive form of responding to change in the workplace (Pedro Marques-Quinteiro et al., 2018). Differently, adaptive performance is a more proactive form of responding to change in the workplace because it involves anticipation. Adaptive performance can be defined as adjusting to job situational demand (Pulakos, Arad, Donovan, & Plamondon, 2000). A worker who is versatile is likely to be valued due to his contributions to the success of an organization. Employers look for employees with high adaptability in an organization that have ability to handle stress, display excellent work performance and positive outcomes (Leiz, Niessan & Sarowsky, 2009). Jund et al. (2014) defined adaptive performance of employees as the ability and willingness of an employee to change to any work situation. Similarly, adaptive performance in the work environment also refers to adjusting to and understanding change in the workplace. It is an employee's ability to adapt to rapidly changing work situations (Towler, 2020). In same vein, Shoss, Witt, and Vera (2012) posited that adaptive performance can occur in anticipation of changes, in response to environmental changes.

Adaptive performance reflects the need to clearly address employees' adaptability to the changes in the work environment. At the individual level, adaptive performance is an employee's ability to adapt to rapidly changing work situations (Park & Park, 2019). When an employee is adaptive this can lead to improved job performance and career success (Park & Park, 2019). At the organizational level, when employees are adaptive, this can lead to gains in change management, organizational learning and customer satisfaction (Park & Park, 2019). The idea of adaptability from the capacity of workers that behave in a certain way, actually demonstrate through their performance (McLoughlin & Priyadarshini, 2021). Adaptive performance includes solving problems creatively, dealing with uncertainty, learning new tasks, demonstrating interpersonal adaptability, and handling crises (Towler 2020).

However, adaptation can be either reactive or proactive; employees need to modify their behaviours in relation to changes in workplace environment. These changes are externally determined in reactive adaptation and self-initiated in proactive adaptation (Pulakos, Arad, Donovan, & Plamondon 2000). Huang et al. (2014), made the distinction between reactive adaptive performance and proactive adaptive performance based on eight dimensions of adaptive performance highlighted by Pulakos et al. (2000). Reactive adaptive performance includes the five dimensions: (1) handling emergencies and crisis, (2) managing work stress, (3) dealing with uncertain and unpredictable work situations, (4) cultural adaptability, and (5) physical adaptability. On the other hand, proactive adaptive performance includes the three dimensions: (1) solving problems creatively, (2) training and learning effort, and (3) interpersonal adaptability.

Reactive adaptive performance is described as the employee's ability to modify their behavior in relation to a change in the environment" (Dorsey et al., 2010). This is done by "responding constructively to unexpected and new circumstances (Griffin et al., 2010). Proactive adaptive performance is referred to "an attempt to shape the environment" (Dorsey et al., 2010). This is done by "self-initiated and future-oriented action that aims to change the situation on oneself" (Griffin et al., 2010). Thus, the distinction between reactive and proactive adaptive performance has been made in recent literature.

Job Stress and Employees Adaptive Performance

The most important apprehensions in the study of work stress are the adverse impact on employee's adaptive performance. Employees suffering with stress at work place require ability to build capacity in order to adapt and perform complex tasks. Adaptive performance regards different forms of work-related adaptation. Whereas adaptability regards the degree to which individuals cope with, respond to and/or support changes that affect their roles as individuals (Pedro Marques-Quinteiro et al., 2018). When employees are able to change and are versatile in their performance and ways of working, this can lead to important changes within the organization that promote success. Individuals who excel in adaptability have a more positive attitude in their work and have a better ability to handle stress (Towler, 2020). Besides, when employees can adapt to change, they are better able to deal with

workplace stressors and utilize effective coping strategies to deal with stress; this can lead to positive organizational changes (Towler, 2020). However, being able to handle stress is particularly important, especially when an organization is experiencing disruptions from the external environment. Work stressors can decrease an employee's ability to perform well and is linked to nonproductive performance and turnover (Agolla & Ongori, 2008).

The research on employee adaptive performance offers a deeper understanding of the dynamic nature of individual performance under conditions of unpredictability (Pulakos et al., 2000). Because scholars and practitioners agree on the importance of adaptive performance in the workplace (e.g., Shoss, Witt, & Vera, 2012) and there are studies detailing the drivers of adaptive performance (e.g., Hans & Williams, 2008), very little is still known regarding the relationship between job stress and adaptive performance. However, job stress has been studied widely in relation to the performance of employees (Adetayo, Ajani and Olabisi, 2014; Warraich, Ahmed, Ahmad and Khoso, 2014). Thus, employee performance is a quite broad concept with many underlying dimensions. Most recent studies only examined the relationship between job stress and employees' performance but did not exhibit adaptive performance.

Few studies examined the relationships between individual characteristics of employees in relationships and adaptive performance (Enchakoui, 2013; Sawyer et al., 2018), others studied contextual variables in relationship to adaptive performance (Ghitulescu, 2013; Zhang & Li, 2016; Charbonnier et al; 2010). However, no current studies have related job stress to adaptive performance. For that reason, this present study, therefore, fill the gap by empirically investigate the effect of job stress on employees' adaptive performance.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical underpinning of this study stems from two theories; role theory and person- environment fit.

Role Theory

One of the basic premises of the role theory is that various occupational roles that individuals engage in may be stressful, regardless of their actual occupation, suggesting that stress found in various work roles may be stressful for all workers. Osipow and Spokane (1987) identify six work roles that they felt were stressful, regardless of an individual's actual vocational choice. These six roles were also utilized in the revised version of the OSI and include: (a) role ambiguity, (b) role insufficiency, (c) role overload, (d) role boundary, (e) responsibility, and (e) physical environment (Osipow and Spokane, 1987; Osipow, 1998).

Person-Environment Fit

A review of the literature suggests that researchers have attempted to find an explanation regarding the potential relationships that exist between stress, an individual, and the environment. It has been theorized that if there is not an accurate fit between the person and the environment, strain will occur (French, Caplan, and Harrison, 1982). More specifically, a person environment (P-E) fit suggests that

individuals fit certain occupations based on the interaction of a multitude of variables. Theoretically, P-E fit “predicts that the magnitude of strain experienced by an individual is proportional to the degree of misfit between the individual and their occupation” (Pithers and Soden, 1999). Individuals “vary in their needs and abilities just as jobs vary in their incentives and demands” (French et al., 1982). Lazarus and Folkman (1986) believe that the interaction between how an individual affects the environment and vice versa is a complex bi-directional process that is a result of a variety of factors and not any single variable.

The P-E fit theory has attracted researchers who believe there is some efficacy in its' relationship to stress (Pithers and Soden, 1999; Sutherland et al., 1995). This theory was lent some empirical evidence by Sutherland et al. (1995). Their research supported the idea that stress and strain is “inversely related to measures of P-E fit” (Sutherland et al., 1995). Both the OSI (Osipow and Spokane, 1987) and the OSI-R (Osipow, 1998) mention the need for further validation studies to examine P-E fit and the relationship to stress and strain. Person–environment fit (PE) theory offers a framework for assessing and predicting how characteristics of the employee and the work environment jointly determine worker well-being and, in the light of this knowledge, how a model for identifying points of preventive intervention may be elaborated.

Theoretical Synthesis

In line with the role theory, Kahn, Wolfe, Quinn & Rosenthal (1964) posited that role theory was developed to provide insight into the processes that affect the physical and emotional state of an individual in the workplace. Roles can provide connection to other people and access to resources, which in turn may promote feelings of security, status enhancement, and ego gratification. Roles also provide directions for behaviour in otherwise uncertain situations (Hogg, 2000), which may serve to reduce stress and improve well-being.

In the same vein, person-environment fit is associated with the role theory which view that an individual not only influences his or her environment, but the environment also affects the individual which may tends to create stress. In other words, the adequacy of this fit between a person and the environment can affect the person's motivation, behaviour, and overall mental and physical health; that is, if the fit is optimal, the individual's functioning may be facilitated; if it is unsuitable, the individual may experience maladaptation (Holmbeck & Zurenda, 2008).

Research Methodology

The study employed survey research design and descriptive type was used because it produces quantitative information, a valuable tool for assessing opinions, and analyzes several variables simultaneously (Babbie, 1986; Neuman, 1994). The population of the study is the entire staff of selected banks in Lagos state, Nigeria, namely; GTBank and Access Bank Plc. A total of two hundred (200) respondents were drawn from two branches of each bank in Ikeja and Victoria Island in Lagos

State as the studied population. The selection was based on different categories of the employees. A sample size of 133 respondents were chosen using Yaro Yamani method while the which sampling technique was used to select a portion of the population to represent the target population in order to give true representation and accuracy of the research result. Therefore, 133 respondents were selected through simple random sampling from the population. This is because it gives every element in the population an equal chance of being selected in the sample size. This sampling technique was applied where the study selects a group of different categories of staff of the bank based on the length of service. This study was also guided by certain demographic parameters such as gender, age, marital status and educational qualifications. Correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the data collected. Correlation matrix shows the relationship between various variables of interest to the research hypotheses while regression analysis allows the prediction of an outcome on one variable (dependent variable) on the basis of several other variables (independent variable).

Model Specification

In this study, three dimensions of job stress in banking industry were analyzed to determine if they have an effect or influence on employees' adaptive performance, and this is in line with the formulated objectives. The structural model was stated as follows:

$$y = \alpha + \beta_1\chi_1 + \beta_2\chi_2 + \beta_3\chi_3 + u \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Thus, the model can be re-specified in the following form;

$$EAP = \alpha + \beta_1JR + \beta_2EPMC + \beta_3WE + u \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: EAP= Employee's Adaptive performance; JR = Job roles; EPMC = Employee's physical and mental conditions; WE = Work environment

Measurement of Variables

The independent variable (Job stress) was measured by using different job stress dimensions such as work environment, employee's physical and mental condition, job roles while employees' adaptive performance was captured by overall adaptive performance and measured by behavioral dimensions (e.g., coping with changes, learning). Of the 133 copies of questionnaires that were distributed, 120 copies of questionnaires were filled and returned. The valid responses were used for the analysis. The Likert research instrument was used to analyse data whose validity and reliability has been tested over the years (Oleabhiele & Asekome, 2019).

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Job stress has no significant impact on employees' adaptive performance

Table 1 Regression Results for the Impact of Job Stress on Employee’s Adaptive Performance

		Statistic	P-Value
R Squared		0.969	
Adjusted R ²		0.968	
F-Statistic (df, n)		551.7(3, 117)	0.000
	Coefficients	Statistics	P-Value
Constant	0.041	0.062	0.008
Job roles	0.109	0.790	0.043
Employee’s physical and mental conditions	0.829	0.625	0.046
Work environment	0.135	0.678	0.000

Source: Researcher’ Computation using SPSS

The results show that the F statistic is 551.7 with a P value of 0.000; therefore, the explanatory variables are jointly significant in explaining variations in the dependent variable. The constant coefficient is significant at 0.041, P = 0.008, < 0.05, implying that the independent variables jointly explain the variations in employees' adaptive performance.

Job roles coefficient is significant at = 0.109, P < 0.05 this indicates that there is a significant (Positive) relationship between job roles and adaptive performance, employee's physical and mental conditions coefficient is also significant at = 0.829, P=0.046 that shows that employee's physical and mental conditions has influence on adaptive performance. Based on the findings, work environment coefficient is significant at = 0.135, P= 0.000, implying that work environment has effect on adaptive performance of employees. According to the regression model estimated, the model as fitted explains 97 percent of the total variability in employees' adaptive performance. In other words, the variability changes in the employees' adaptive performance could be accounted for by approximately 97% of factors related to job stress while 3% of the total variability in employees' adaptive performance can be explained by other variables. This implies that job stress is a good predictor of employees' adaptive performance. This is in line with Udu and Eke (2018) who argued that occupational stress significantly affect the performance of female bankers in different ways.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the job stress and employees' adaptive performance

Table 2 Correlation Matrix of Variables

		EAP	JR	EPMC	WE
EAP	Pearson Correlation	1	.679**	.799**	.483**
JR	Pearson Correlation	.679**	1	.456**	.487**
EPMC	Pearson Correlation	.799**	.456**	1	.896**
WE	Pearson Correlation	.483**	.487**	.896**	1

Source: Researcher’ Computation using SPSS

The correlation table above clearly shows that significant relationship exists between different job stress dimensions (job roles, work environment, and employee's physical and mental condition) and employee's adaptive performance. These results are unexpected and completely negate the claims that job stress is negatively related to job performance. In fact, there is positive relationship among the different job stress dimensions and employee's adaptive performance. Although, there are higher levels of stress in the banking sector, however, due to better conditions in certain areas, for instance, control over work and support at work, the employees can perform well and stress is unable to retard the performance of the employees. This result is supported by the finding of Park and Park (2019) which they found 13 contextual characteristics affecting adaptive performance: decision-making autonomy, job demands, job resources, job uncertainty, and role change as job characteristics (six); support from coworkers and supervisors, transformational leadership, and team climate as group characteristics (three); and clear vision, climate for innovation, organizational support, and learning organization as organizational characteristics (four).

H₀: Stressors have no influence on adaptive performance of employees

Table 3 Regression Results

		Statistic	P-Value
R Squared		.926	
Adjusted R Square		.922	
F-Statistic (df, n)	(2, 118)	217.699	0.001
	Coefficients	Statistics	P-Value
Constant	.231	.082	0.006
Stressors	.072	.123	0.000

Source: Researcher' Computation using SPSS

This could be written in model form as: $EAP = 0.231 + 0.072x$ where EAP = "Employees' adaptive performance" and x = "Stressor"

Table 3 shows that the analysis of variance of the fitted regression equation is significant with F value of 217.699. This is an indication that the model is a good one. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, it shows a statistically significant relationship between the variables at 95 percent confidence level. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected. Thus, accept alternative hypothesis (H₁) stressors have influence on employees' adaptive performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Stress is a natural human response to its environment. Stress has become significant due to dynamic social factor and changing needs of life styles. Stress is man's adaptive reaction to an outward situation which would lead to physical, mental and behavioural changes. In fact, moderate levels of stress are considered essential motivators. However, high levels of stress have the capacity to greatly impact

physical and emotional health, not all stresses are destructive in nature. Appropriate amount of stress can actually trigger passion for work, tap latent abilities and even ignite inspirations. Stress can make a person productive and constructive, when it is identified and well managed. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. Bank managers and supervisors should increase employees' ability to be autonomous in their work roles.
2. Bank managers should pay extra attention to job roles in order to avoid or reduce distortions of responsibilities.
3. Bank managers should prioritise employees' well-being and make sure that employee can adapt to either situations, or that the right employees are in the right position to deal with the situations they encounter.
4. They should make physical working environment more conducive and less stress by expanding employee's working station to avoid overcrowding.
5. Bank managers should adjust their leadership style to the different individuals, hereby, trying to achieve the most optimal effects of the job stress on adaptive performance.
6. Managers can give positive feedback and provide rewards to encourage adaptive performance.
7. They have a strong adaptive organizational culture that is more likely to survive within the business environment.

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